

Myth 4: Posting a preprint online means I don't need to think about copyright or licensing

YouTube Description Box

Have you heard the claim, “I’m posting my preprint online, so I don’t need to think about copyright or licensing”? 🤔

In this episode of the **ASAPbio Myth Busting Series**, we unpack why copyright and licensing still matter when sharing your preprint. From understanding your automatic copyright rights to choosing the right Creative Commons license, we’ll explore how these decisions shape reuse, visibility, and journal publication.

🌟 **Bottom line:** Posting a preprint doesn’t erase copyright—it makes your licensing choices even more important.

⚖️ Disclaimer

The information in this video is intended for educational purposes only and does **not** constitute legal advice. Copyright and licensing laws vary by country—consult your institutional experts or an attorney for guidance.

📖 References & Resources

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🔗 Zenodo link: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17154631

🌐 Learn more at <https://asapbio.org>

🔔 Don't forget to like, comment, and subscribe for more myth-busting insights about preprints and open science!

Script

Camera 1/2

Welcome to the ASAPbio Myth Busting Series. Today, we’ll delve into this statement: “I’m posting my preprint online, so I don’t need to think about copyright or licensing.”

It sounds simple, right? But here is the truth: copyright and licensing matter just as much for preprints as they do for any other form of publication.

Camera 3

Let's start with some copyright basics. The moment you write your manuscript, you automatically hold copyright. No forms to fill out, no registration. Copyright gives you control over the distribution, reproduction, and adaptation of your work.

Of course, copyright laws are not identical worldwide. In this video, we will cover general principles, but be sure to check your local regulations and talk to your library, legal, or intellectual property experts for region-specific advice.

So... Posting your paper on a preprint server does **not** erase your copyright. In fact, it raises important questions: how do you want others to use your work?

Camera 4/5/6/7

This is where licensing comes in. Most preprint servers ask you to choose a license when you post. Licenses are like permission slips—They tell readers what they can and can't do with your work.

Creative Commons licenses are widely used for preprints. These licenses have a CC icon on the left, followed by icons and simple language that indicate if and how others can use, share, or build on your work.

- This icon and “SA” mean that someone can change your work, but their version must be shared under the same license as yours
- This icon and “NC” mean that only non-commercial uses are permitted
- This icon and “ND” mean that no one can make changes to the original work

All Creative Commons licenses give credit to the original creator, indicated with this icon and “BY”

Lastly, CC0 places work in the public domain, waiving all copyright.

Of note, while some preprint servers ask you to choose from a range of license options, others may require a CC BY license. Some funders may also have specific requirements. It's important to take these into consideration when making your choices.

Camera 8 - Clip 4

In practice, license selection for preprinting varies widely.¹

[BRIEF PAUSE – TO DISPLAY FIGURE]

What happens if you don't think about licensing? You are not alone. But you risk creating confusion. Without clear terms, other researchers may not know whether they can reuse your figures, translate your work, or text-mine for future studies. You may even restrict legitimate reuse of your work without intending to.

To maximize visibility and impact, consider using an open license such as CC BY, which ensures your preprint can be widely shared and reused with attribution

Camera 9 - Clip 5

What if you want to publish your manuscript in a journal? Preprint servers can require authors to grant them a *perpetual, non-exclusive* license to **distribute** the preprint.^{2,3} This is **not** the same as a copyright transfer.

Most of the time, you retain copyright – so you can still license or transfer it to a publisher later. Still, always check the terms of the preprint server and your target journal to make sure they align!

Camera 10

In summary, when done right, licensing has real benefits:

- It can protect your intent—for example, if you only want to allow non-commercial use, a CC BY-NC license makes that clear
- It can also boost your impact – open licenses like CC BY make it easier for others to reuse, translate, and build upon your work, increasing visibility

Camera 11

So let's revisit our myth: I'm posting my preprint online, so I don't need to think about copyright or licensing.

¹ Fraser N, Brierley L, Dey G, Polka JK, Pálffy M, Nanni F, Coates JA. 2021. The evolving role of preprints in the dissemination of COVID-19 research and their impact on the science communication landscape. *PLoS Biol* 19:e3000959. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.3000959

² arXiv.org - Non-exclusive license to distribute. 2004. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/licenses/nonexclusive-distrib/1.0/license.html>

³ Rye S. 2025. Copyright and Licensing for Preprints. *Preprints.org*. <https://www.preprints.org/blog/post/copyright-licensing-preprints>

Actually, copyright is automatic, and licensing is your active choice. Preprints don't remove the need to think carefully—they make it even more important. By choosing the right license, you protect your work, support open science, and make it easier for others to build responsibly on your ideas.

[PAUSE – TO DISPLAY DISCLAIMER (Camera 12)]

Camera 13

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